

Factors Of Development Of Educational Competencies Of Future Teachers Through Problem Educational Technologies

Usmanov Adkham Abdukhamidovich

Nizamiy Tashkent State Pedagogical University, Faculty of Military Education,
senior teacher of the cycle of military training, associate professor

Abstract: *The article details the factors for the development of educational competencies for teachers of military education up to the upcoming call through problematic educational technologies and the pedagogical aspects of the development of educational activities of students of military educational faculties through problematic educational technologies.*

Keywords — problem-based education, problem, problem situation, heuristic methods, thinking, creative thinking, knowledge, intellectual.

INTRODUCTION.

The effect of the reforms carried out in the educational system of our country in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the “concept for the development of Higher Education until 2030” is emphasized in directing the national education system to achieve a new result as “a new system of universal knowledge, skills, qualifications, as well as the experience of independent activities and personal responsibility of [1]

Based on problem teaching, the American psychologist, philosopher and educator Dj. The ideas of dui (1859-1952) lie. He founded the Chicago City Training School in 1894, an experimental school where games and labor activities formed rather than a curriculum. Training in reading, counting, writing was carried out in accordance with the spontaneous needs of children, depending on their physiological puberty. [2]

The deep study of problem teaching began in the 60s of the XX century. The idea and principles of problematic teaching from the point of view of the psychology of thinking S.L.Rubinstein, M.I.Makhmutov, V.Okon, I.Y.Developed by psychologist scientists such as Lerner. [3,4,5,6]

S.L. Rubinstein's idea that “thinking begins with a problematic situation” has been taken as the psychological basis of problematic teaching. When it was noted that in the 70s and 80s, the effectiveness of traditional forms of teaching declined, leading educators began to focus on problematic teaching theory. [3]

Because in the traditional form of teaching, the main focus is on the activities of the teacher, in the concept of problematic teaching, the main emphasis is shifted to the side of the students. Knowledge on the principle of problematic teaching is not transmitted to students in a ready-made form, but is acquired by students in the process of educational activities, resembling a research process. [8]

Currently, Research in this area is continued in different countries of the world, complex developments of problematic teaching technologies are being created, both in the field of Educational Sciences and in the field of Higher Education.

Problem teaching-organizes the active interaction of the student with the content of the problematic presented education. In this process, the reader approaches the objective contradictions of scientific knowledge and their solutions, learns to think, to creative assimilation of knowledge. [4]

Hence, a problematic issue can be seen as a simple, private case of a problem. Problem teaching is aimed at the formation and development of creative activity as well as the need for it, in the process of which the development of creative thinking of students becomes more intensive than in traditional teaching. But for this function of problem teaching to increase, it is not enough to include a random set of problems in the learning process.

The system of problems should cover the main types of problems inherent in this area of knowledge. When applying problem teaching to the educational process, the teacher must distinguish between scientific and educational problems and the difference. Their commonality is that both have objective contradictions, the difference between scientific and educational problems is that the problem posed in the scientific problem has not yet been solved, and in the educational problem the problem has been solved, the way to solve it and the result is known. The ultimate goal of problem teaching is to teach students to see and solve problems, which is only done in the process of thinking activities. [7]

S.L.Rubinstein argues that “contemplation is the perception that leads to the solution of the issue and problems before a person, and that contemplation arises from a problem situation and is aimed at solving the problem”. [3]

From this, the following logic is derived. The fact that an individual is creative, independent, thinking is necessary for society, and the process of thinking begins with a problematic situation. A problem situation is a psychic difficulty, a conflict situation in which the ability to think is developed by lowering students into a problem situation. Problem teaching methods include: research method, heuristic method, method of creating problem situations.

The role of heuristic methods in the development of creative thinking Heuristic methods, for example, increase the likelihood of finding a workable but not always optimal

solution to a creative issue where initial data is generated either full or unreliable. Heuristic techniques make it possible to find a solution even in very complex, not foreseen situations. Heuristics defines a style of action that promotes the achievement of the goal. [5]

Heuristica (Greek *heurisko* – I am looking for, finding, discovering) develops within the limits of psychology, cybernetics, structural linguistics, information theory as a science that studies human creative activity, as well as the methods used to create new discoveries. Heuristics can be understood as the science that studies the laws of building new actions in a new situation.

Contemplation is a generalized and abstract reflection process in which the objects of cognition of the human mind ensure the presence of complex, all-round connections between what is calculated and phenomena. The process of understanding, understanding and conscious attitude towards the world is called thinking, thinking.

In problem education, three methods stand out: problem presentation, partial search, and research. Problem presentation explanation is an intermediate method that implies the transition from an illustrative type to an actual problem education. A problematic presentation does not give Ready-Made knowledge (which is common for information presentation), but the problem opens up as a search for scientific truth. [7]

The problem task is an element of the educational process. To create a state of intellectual tension between teachers of military education up to the upcoming call, they are given questions, assignments, exercises, difficulties (conflicts) in the process of performing them are identified.

Disadvantages of problem teaching include the fact that it takes time (according to ready-made knowledge) rather than information. Problem education often goes beyond a single lesson. But his qualities are superior to his weaknesses. Until the upcoming call, we consider it advisable to apply military education teachers as a methodological system in the development of their creative qualities. [8]

Until the upcoming Call, teachers of military education see themselves in the role of participants (partners), explorers in the search for truth. Thus, with a problematic statement, the head of the training himself forms a problem, puts a problematic task, determines complex ways to solve it, as if conducting research and giving results.

Depending on the complexity of the problem, the level of knowledge of the teachers of military education up to the upcoming Call, its intellectual salience and qualifications, their skills in creative activities, orientation towards didactic goals, it is likely that in the relationship of the teachers of military education and professors up to the upcoming call there will be different situations and halates, that is.

The main conditions for the implementation of problematic education in the educational process of the faculties of military education as one of the methods of developing the creative qualities of teachers of military education up to the upcoming

Call: development of teaching aids in Educational Sciences, which include a complex of problematic theoretical and practical tasks; implementation of the targeted work of interdisciplinary commissions of cycles; in problem training, it is necessary for the leaders of the training to increase the level of universal and pedagogical skill and organize their upbringing as a mature specialist.

References

- [1] National database of legislative acts of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 “on approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” PF-5847 //, – T., 2019. 09.10.2019 y. 06/19/5847/3887.
- [2] Dewey J. Individualization of school education. –Chicago: 1991, –198 p.
- [3] Rubinstein S.L. Fundamentals of general psychology // Pedagogy, Moscow: 1989, p. 326.
- [4] Makhmutov M. I. Organization of problem-based learning at school // Young scientist. – M. 2020. - pp. 257-259.
- [5] Okon V. Fundamentals of problem-based learning: trans. from Polish. M.: Enlightenment, 1968. 208 p.
- [6] Lerner I.Y. Didakticheskiye osnovi metodov obucheniya. – Moskva: Pedagogika, 1981.
- [7] Skatkin M.N. Problems of modern didactics // Pedagogy, – M., 1984. – p. 96.
- [8] Avliekulov N.H. Musayeva N.N. Teacher of technology. – T, Garden of Thought, 2012. – B. 80.